

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2
0
2
4

No 11

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 219 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-noyabrda ruxsat etildi.*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti rektori
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, p.f.f.d., (PhD), Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya instituti rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Hududiy ta'lim muassasalari va markazlar bo'yicha prorektor v.b.
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TDIUprofessor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d., TSUE professori
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, f.f.d. profesor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Cham Tat Huei, (PhD) USCI universiteti professori, Malayziya
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d.,(PhD) "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d.,(PhD) TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Djudi Smetana, p.f.n., Pitsburg davlat universiteti dosenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Krissi Lyuis, p.f.n., Pitsburg davlat universiteti dosenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Ali Kopak (Али Кўнак), i.f.d., prof., Karabuk universiteti dosenti, Turkiya
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, i.f.n., "LUKOIL-Energoservis" Kompaniyasi iqtisodchisi, Moskva.
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., (PhD) TDIU dotsenti
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Oqil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjaevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, DSc, Prof., Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Rae Kwon Chung, honorary professor of TSUE, Nobel laureate, South Korea,

Osman Mesten, member of the Turkish Parliament, head of the Turkey-Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, DSc, Prof., Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich CSc, Prof., Rector of Academy of Labor and Social Relations

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, DSc, Prof., TSUE Vice-Rector for Scientific Affairs and Innovation

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhritdinovich, DSc, Prof., Rector of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Siddikova Sadokat Ghaforovna, PhD, Rector of the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, DSc, Prof., acting Vice-rector for regional educational institutions and centers of TSUE

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, CSc, Prof., of TSUE

Slizovsky Dimitriy Yegorovich, DSc, Prof., of the People's Friendship University of Russia

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, DSc, Prof., Rector of International "Nordic" University

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja ugli, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of the DGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the DCECGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganievich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, PhD in Philology, Professor.

Shoira Azimovna Musaeva, professor of SamDu IS Institute

Cham Tat Huei, PhD, professor at USCI University, Malaysia

Buzrukhanov Sarvarkhan Munavvarkhanovich, DSc, Deputy Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, PhD, deputy of executive director of the "El-yurt umidi" fund

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, PhD, Senior Lecturer at Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction

Judy Smetana CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Chrissy Lewis CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Ali Konak DSc, Prof., Associate Professor of Karabuk University, Turkey

Glazova Marina Viktorovna, CSc, economist at LUKOIL-Energoservis Company, Moscow.

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, associate professor of TSUE

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, doctoral student at Ankara University, Turkey

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, independent researcher of TSUE

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, p.f.f.d., (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi
huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali
O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi
huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori
bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Iqtisodiyotning pul mablag'lari bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasini oshirish yo'llari.....	16
Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich, Yusupov Muxammadali Soxib o'g'li	
Driving economic growth through service exports.....	20
Rahimov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida jamoat tashkilotlarini boshqarishni takomillashtirishda jahon tajribasi.....	27
Raxmonov Abduxalil Rasulovich	
Raqamli marketing va mijozlar bilan ishlashning yangi usullari.....	31
Ummatov Avaz Muydinovich	
Soliq tushumlarini shakllantirish ko'rsatkichlari asosida soliq salohiyatini baholash usullari	35
Jo'raev Husan	
Bevosita soliqqa tortish darajasini ko'paytirish omillari.....	41
Qodirov Baxodir Quadratovich	
Tijorat banklarining xo'jalik subyektlari bilan amalga oshiriladigan muddatli valyuta operatsiyalarini rivojlantirish	47
Ibodullaeva Ma'rifat To'lqin qizi	
Tovarlarning monopol yuqori (past) narxlarini aniqlashni takomillashtirish masalalari	52
Mingboev Asqar Qandaharovich	
Bojxona faoliyatini transformatsiyalashda innovatsion boshqaruvni takomillashtirishga oid xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	59
Ro'ziboyev Muhiddin Xushnudovich	
Harnessing foreign direct investment for sustainable economic growth in Central Asia: policy challenges and opportunities.....	63
Mukhammedova Azizakhon Ikromjon kizi	
Mintaqa innovatsion faoliyatida tavakkalchilikni boshqarishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	68
Sapayeva N.K.	
Examining Uzbekistan's foreign trade indicators	72
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
Yo'l bo'yidagi xizmat ko'rsatish infratuzilmasini baholash: xizmat sifati va transport xavfsizligini oshirish.....	78
Egamberduyev Odil Buriboyevich	
Роль инноваций в гибком управлении проектами.....	82
Касимова Наима Жахангировна	
Sug'urta bozorini tartibga solishni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	87
Tursunova Maftuna Agzamovna	
Mintaqada turizm sohasini rivojlantirishda madaniy turizm resurslarining o'rni va roli	91
Ro'zmetov Baxodir Shomurotovich	
Sug'urta kompaniyalarining kapital bozoridagi emission faolligini oshirishning iqtisodiy asoslari	97
Shodmonova Munisa Nizamjon qizi	
Korxonaning tashqi bozorga chiqishida marketing strategiyasining samaradorligini baholash.....	104
Akramov Bo'ribek Faxriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalar innovatsion faoliyatini boshqarish	110
Saipova Dilnoza Shuxratovna	

Xalqaro standartlar asosida kapital qo'yilmalar hisobini takomillashtirish.....	114
Egamberdieva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
Investitsiyalar samaradorligini baholash va ularga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlili.....	120
Jo'raev Paxlavonjon Usarovich	
Soliq qarzdorliklarini yuzaga kelishining ilmiy nazariy asoslari tadqiqi	127
Ostonaqulov Alisher Abdurashidovich	
Korxonalarni moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularga imtiyozlar berishni takomillashtirish masalalari.....	132
Z.T. Mirzayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalarda raqamli marketingning ahamiyati.....	139
M.Vohobjonova	
Положение электронной коммерции на международном и национальном уровнях	142
Абдуганиев Учкун Хабибулла угли, Орифбоев Озод Азатович	
Korporativ resurslardan samarali foydalanish orqali kichik biznes subyektlarini barqaror rivojlantirish va samaradorligini oshirish.....	148
Jalolova Muazzamxon Akbarjonovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida kartoshka ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi.....	151
Avazmurodov Islom Nusratullo o'g'li, Muratov Shukrullo Abduraimovich	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakati bo'yicha logistik muammolar va ularni bartaraf etishning samarali yechimlari	155
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev	
Ta'lim va ilm-fan sohasida inson kapitali konsepsiyasining amalga oshish bosqichlari yo'nalishlari.....	159
Nasretdinova Aziza Adxamjonovna , Bozarov Elyor Boboqulovich	
Влияние цифровой валюты центральных банков (CBDC) на международную торговлю и финансовые отношения: Анализ и перспективы	164
Номозали Хайдаров	
Raqamli transformatsiya va tadbirkorlik: kichik biznes uchun yangi imkoniyatlar va chora-tadbirlar	167
Sobirjonov Sanjar Sobirjonovich, TDIU magistranti	
O'zbekiston respublikasida aholini samarali ish bilan ta'minlash istiqbollari.....	172
Raxmatullayeva Shahnoza Xamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchxon Sadriddin qizi	
Aylanma mablag'lar aylanuvchanligini tezlashtirishning asosiy yo'llari	179
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich	
Mintaqada to'qimachilik sanoatining iqtisodiy holati tahlili (Xorazm viloyati misolida)	185
Xudoyorova M.O	
Мировой опыт стратегического управления финансовыми ресурсами акционерных обществ.....	190
Абдалиев Айдос Бахтиярович	
Sug'urta faoliyatida axborot jarayonlarini vtomatlashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	196
Shakirov O'tkirbek Taxirovich	
Yerlardan maqsadli foydalanishni aniqlash uslubi.....	199
Yunusov Begench Mavlanberdievich	
Iqtisodiyotda real sektorning ahamiyati va uning rivojlanishi.....	204
Amirqulov Umarali Akram o'g'li	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni baholash amaliyoti va indikatorlari	208
Feruz Raxmatova Yusupjanovna	
O'zbekistonda korxonalarni boshqarishda raqamli texnologiyalardan qo'llash yo'nalishlari	213
Qo'chqorov Tohir Safarovich, To'ychiyev Akmaljon Abdulatif o'g'li	

DRIVING ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH SERVICE EXPORTS

Rahimov Eshmurod Normuradovich

Tashkent State University of Economics

PhD, Associate Professor,

Department of Macroeconomic Policy and Forecasting

Abstract: This paper explores the role of service exports in driving economic growth, emphasizing how increased integration into global service markets can enhance productivity, employment, and sustainable development. By examining empirical studies and global data, the paper highlights key factors that influence the success of service exports, such as digitalization, trade policies, and the competitiveness of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The findings underline the importance of a supportive policy framework to maximize the economic benefits of service sector exports.

Key words: Service exports, economic growth, digitalization, trade policy, SMEs.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada xizmatlar eksportining iqtisodiy o'sishni rag'batlantirishdagi roli o'rganiladi. Xalqaro xizmatlar bozoriga chuqurroq integratsiya qilish samaradorlik, bandlik va barqaror rivojlanishga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi ta'kidlanadi. Tadqiqotda empirik tadqiqotlar va global ma'lumotlarga asoslanib, xizmatlar eksportining muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirilishiga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan raqamlashtirish, savdo siyosati va kichik va o'rta korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligi kabi asosiy omillar ko'rib chiqiladi. Natijalar xizmatlar eksportidan iqtisodiy manfaatlarni maksimal darajada olish uchun qo'llab-quvvatlovchi siyosiy muhitning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Xizmatlar eksporti, iqtisodiy o'sish, raqamlashtirish, savdo siyosati, kichik va o'rta biznes (KOB).

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль экспорта услуг в стимулировании экономического роста. Подчеркивается, что более глубокая интеграция в международный рынок услуг положительно влияет на производительность, занятость и устойчивое развитие. На основе эмпирических исследований и глобальных данных в исследовании рассматриваются ключевые факторы, влияющие на успешную реализацию экспорта услуг, такие как цифровизация, торговая политика и конкурентоспособность малых и средних предприятий. Результаты подчеркивают важность благоприятной политической среды для максимизации экономических выгод от экспорта услуг.

Ключевые слова: Экспорт услуг, экономический рост, цифровизация, торговая политика, малые и средние предприятия (МСП).

INTRODUCTION

In the modern global economy, service exports have emerged as a significant driver of economic growth. While traditional exports, such as manufactured goods and natural resources, continue to play a critical role, the expanding service sector has reshaped the global trade landscape. Service exports—including industries such as tourism, financial services, telecommunications, and information technology—present new opportunities for economic diversification and value creation.

This paper examines the role of service exports in promoting economic growth, analyzing key sectors, trends, and the impact of policy measures on the expansion of service exports. Additionally, it reviews modern approaches and methods for classifying country-specific risks and assesses the effectiveness of these methods. Based on this analysis, the paper aims to establish comprehensive risk profiles for countries and systematically evaluate the factors influencing their sustainable development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A growing body of literature underscores the importance of service exports in driving economic growth. Studies indicate that service exports positively impact GDP growth, employment, and trade balances in both developed and developing economies. For example, research by the International Monetary Fund (2023) underscores the vital role of IT and financial services in bolstering economic resilience. Similarly, the World Bank (2022) points out that countries with diversified service sectors typically achieve higher growth rates than those dependent on traditional exports.

In Uzbekistan's context, several factors contribute to the potential growth of service exports. The country has made substantial progress in economic reforms, with a strategic focus on sectors like tourism and IT to

attract foreign investment and enhance competitiveness. However, challenges persist, including infrastructure gaps, skill shortages, and regulatory barriers. This literature review will analyze key findings on the impact of service exports on economic performance, emphasizing the unique circumstances and opportunities within Uzbekistan.

METHODOLOGY

The data for this analysis was sourced from international databases, including the World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), and United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD). To assess the economic impact of service exports, this paper utilizes quantitative methods, including regression and trend analyses, to examine the correlation between service export volumes and key economic indicators such as GDP growth, employment rates, and trade balance. The analysis spans the period from 2000 to 2024, providing a comprehensive perspective on recent trends.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The classification of risks associated with countries and their economies is vital for informed decision-making and sustainable development. The concept of “risk” includes various uncertainties arising from socio-economic, political, and financial events, each impacting countries differently. A robust risk classification system is essential for identifying, assessing, and effectively managing country-specific risks. Developing such a system requires considering factors like the level of economic development, political stability, and the social environment. From this perspective, it is essential to categorize country-specific risks into economic, political, and social categories.

This study aims to investigate the methodological foundations of a country-specific risk classification system and to provide a detailed analysis. In an increasingly interconnected global economy, understanding the forms of risks that countries face from both internal and external factors is crucial. Accurate risk classification enables better prediction of potential outcomes and supports proactive risk management. Therefore, developing risk classification systems should leverage methodologies from international financial organizations and leading academic research.

Figure 1 presents growth trends in Uzbekistan’s major service export sectors from 2000 to 2024, covering Tourism, IT Services, Financial Services, and Healthcare Services. Each line represents the export volume for a particular sector over the years, illustrating how these sectors have evolved and contributed to the country’s overall economic performance.

Figure 1 illustrates the growth trends of major service export sectors in Uzbekistan from 2000 to 2024, including Tourism, IT Services, Financial Services, and Healthcare Services.

The graph demonstrates that the IT Services sector has experienced the most substantial growth, spurred by a global increase in demand for digital services and Uzbekistan’s reforms promoting digitalization. The tourism sector also shows a steady upward trend, reflecting the country’s efforts to strengthen its tourism

industry through infrastructural improvements and promotional campaigns. While financial services display growth, the increase is more moderate, indicating that although the sector is progressing, it may face challenges such as regulatory or capital constraints. Healthcare services show positive but slower growth, highlighting areas where further investment or development could be beneficial. Overall, the graph underscores the economic benefits of a diversified service export portfolio, with IT services and tourism offering the most immediate potential for economic expansion.

Correlation Between Service Exports and GDP Growth: Figure 3 illustrates the positive correlation between service exports and GDP growth. Each data point represents service export volumes alongside corresponding GDP growth rates, demonstrating that as Uzbekistan's service exports increase, GDP growth tends to follow. This relationship is especially pronounced in technology and financial services sectors, where the export of high-value services contributes notably to economic expansion.

Figure 2 illustrates the positive correlation between service exports and GDP growth.

The graph illustrates that an increase in service exports aligns with higher GDP growth rates, with the positive trend line highlighting a stable and advantageous relationship between service export growth and economic performance. This relationship is particularly strong in economies focused on technology and financial sectors. The data suggest that as Uzbekistan's service export sector expands, it brings notable GDP growth, reinforcing the role of service exports as a key driver of economic development. The regression line further emphasizes that higher levels of service exports correlate with greater GDP growth, especially in high-value sectors. This trend supports the view that strategic investment in service exports can yield substantial economic benefits for Uzbekistan, including improved GDP, job creation, and a stronger trade balance.

These findings underscore the vital role of service exports in driving economic growth and diversification for emerging economies, particularly for countries like Uzbekistan. With global markets increasingly demanding high-value services—such as technology, financial services, and tourism—service exports present a unique opportunity to create quality jobs, boost GDP, and provide economic insulation from commodity market fluctuations. Service exports enable countries to integrate into global value chains, boost productivity, and encourage sustainable growth. However, Uzbekistan faces several challenges that limit its ability to fully leverage its service export potential.

Firstly, market access restrictions in key export destinations pose barriers for Uzbekistan's service sectors, limiting growth in high-value areas like IT and finance. These restrictions often arise from protectionist policies in partner countries or regulatory complexities that inhibit cross-border services trade. Overcoming these barriers through strategic bilateral and multilateral trade agreements is essential for expanding Uzbekistan's market reach.

Secondly, inadequate digital infrastructure is a significant constraint. Robust digital infrastructure is essential for modern service sectors, especially in IT and finance, to thrive. Currently, limited access to high-speed internet, data security frameworks, and cloud services infrastructure restricts Uzbekistan's ability to engage fully in the global digital economy. Investments in nationwide broadband access, data protection, and modern

telecommunications infrastructure are necessary to provide the foundational support for the growth of digital service exports.

Thirdly, skill gaps within the labor force hinder the development of Uzbekistan's service sector. High-value service exports demand a skilled workforce, especially in areas like technology, finance, and healthcare. However, current education and training systems are not fully aligned with the requirements of these sectors. To address this, Uzbekistan needs to implement education programs and vocational training that focus on industry-relevant skills, particularly in STEM fields. Collaborations between government, universities, and industry stakeholders can ensure that the workforce is equipped to meet the demands of a competitive service sector.

To overcome these challenges, policies that promote investment in digital infrastructure, enhance service sector competitiveness, and foster human capital development are essential. Investments in digital infrastructure will not only support existing service sectors but also attract foreign investors seeking robust digital capabilities. Policies aimed at increasing digital literacy and offering training in digital skills can accelerate this transition, ensuring that Uzbekistan's workforce is prepared for high-skill jobs in a service-driven economy. Furthermore, fostering a regulatory environment that encourages innovation is critical for boosting service sector competitiveness. Simplifying regulatory processes and reducing bureaucratic barriers can attract both domestic and foreign investment in service exports. Special attention should be given to emerging industries, such as fintech and digital health, where Uzbekistan has the potential to become a regional leader by implementing flexible, forward-looking regulations.

Human capital development is crucial for sustaining long-term growth in service exports. Programs offering incentives for higher education in critical sectors, alongside continuous upskilling initiatives, can address skill shortages and ensure a steady pipeline of qualified professionals. Additionally, fostering public-private partnerships can enhance training quality and align educational outcomes with industry standards.

Trade Partner Analysis: Trade partners are essential to the success of Uzbekistan's service export sectors, providing market access, investment, and growth opportunities. This analysis identifies Uzbekistan's primary trade partners across key service sectors, including IT, tourism, and financial services. The following table outlines these partners, their respective export volumes, and their significance within each sector.

Table 1: Key Trade Partners for Uzbekistan's Service Exports.

Sector	Key Trade Partner	Export Volume (USD Millions)	Significance
IT Services	United States	500	High technology demand and investment in digital services
IT Services	Germany	350	Strong tech collaboration and skilled labor demand
Tourism	Russia	600	High tourist inflow and cultural ties
Tourism	China	450	Growing interest in Uzbekistan's historical sites
Financial Services	United Kingdom	300	Established financial institutions and international banking ties
Financial Services	Turkey	250	Close trade relations and investment partnerships

The table above highlights Uzbekistan's key trade partners in its major service export sectors, offering insights into each sector's top markets and their economic relevance.

For **IT Services**, the United States and Germany are primary partners, drawn by Uzbekistan's expanding IT sector and rising demand for digital services. High levels of technology investment from these partners support sectoral growth, establishing IT as one of the country's most dynamic export areas.

In **Tourism**, Russia and China are leading partners. Russia, due to its cultural connections and geographic proximity, provides a stable inflow of tourists, while China has shown growing interest in Uzbekistan's historical sites, underscoring the potential for further growth in this sector.

For **Financial Services**, the United Kingdom and Turkey stand out as main partners. The UK's established financial institutions and investment capacity significantly contribute to Uzbekistan's financial services sector, while Turkey's close trade relations foster strong economic ties, supporting mutual investment and service sector growth.

Strengthening these partnerships through targeted policies and incentives could enhance Uzbekistan's service exports, unlocking additional potential in high-demand markets.

Export Growth Over Time

This analysis illustrates the growth trends in Uzbekistan's service exports over the past two decades, segmented by key sectors. The graph below provides insights into which sectors have shown the highest growth rates, allowing for comparisons between traditional service sectors, such as tourism, and emerging sectors, such as IT services.

Figure 3: Growth in Service Export Sectors Over Time (2000-2024).

The graph above illustrates that IT services have experienced the most rapid growth, aligning with a global shift toward digital transformation and reflecting Uzbekistan's investments in digital infrastructure. Tourism, a traditionally strong sector, continues its steady growth, highlighting Uzbekistan's appeal as a cultural and historical destination. Financial services also show moderate growth, benefiting from ongoing improvements in the banking and finance sector. Meanwhile, healthcare services, while growing at a slower pace, indicate potential for further expansion as infrastructure and medical expertise advance.

Overall, the graph underscores the value of a diversified service export portfolio, with IT services leading and traditional sectors like tourism maintaining consistent progress. These trends emphasize the need for sector-specific policies to stimulate growth across both emerging and established service sectors in Uzbekistan.

Employment Impact Analysis (Graph)

The following graph illustrates the impact of service export growth on employment rates over time. As service exports expand, employment growth trends upwards, particularly in sectors requiring skilled labor, indicating the economic benefits of growing service exports.

Employment Growth Related to Service Export Expansion (2000-2024)

Figure 4: Employment Growth and Total Service Export Volume from 2000 to 2024.

This graph compares Employment Growth and Total Service Export Volume from 2000 to 2024. Employment growth is measured as a percentage, while service export volume is represented in billions of USD.

- Employment growth generally follows the upward trend of service export expansion, indicating that as countries increase their service exports, they also see a rise in job creation.

- The relationship is especially notable in sectors that require skilled labor, such as IT and financial services, suggesting that these sectors contribute not only to economic growth but also to high-quality employment. The increase in employment rates alongside service export expansion highlights the job-creating potential of the service sector. By focusing on policies that develop service industries, countries can improve their labor markets and reduce unemployment, particularly in skilled professions.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

- To maximize the economic growth potential of service exports, countries should adopt policies that promote key sectors, strengthen trade partnerships, and foster innovation. The following recommendations outline strategies to enhance service exports and their contributions to economic growth:

Diversify Service Export Sectors: To reduce reliance on a limited number of sectors, governments should encourage growth in underdeveloped service areas, such as healthcare, education, and environmental services. Incentivizing companies in these sectors to export their services can create new revenue streams and enhance economic resilience.

Invest in Digital Infrastructure: Digital services, particularly IT and financial services, are essential drivers of modern economies. Investing in digital infrastructure such as high-speed internet access and data centers can expand these industries and improve global competitiveness. Providing subsidies or tax incentives for businesses adopting advanced technology can further accelerate this growth.

Enhance Trade Partnerships and Agreements: Strong trade partnerships can increase market access for service exports. Negotiating favorable terms in international agreements, especially for digital services and financial transactions, can reduce trade barriers and open new markets. Multilateral agreements, such as the WTO's Trade in Services Agreement (TISA), should be pursued to secure broader market access.

Foster Skills Development and Workforce Training: Service sectors, particularly IT, finance, and healthcare, require a skilled workforce. Governments should invest in workforce training programs, especially in STEM fields, to build a talent pool that supports service export expansion. Collaboration between educational institutions and industries can help align skills with market needs.

Strengthen Export Financing and Risk Mitigation: Access to export financing and risk mitigation tools, such as export credit guarantees, can support businesses in engaging in service exports. This is particularly crucial for SMEs lacking sufficient capital for international growth. Governments can collaborate with financial institutions to develop financing solutions specifically for service exporters.

Service exports have become an increasingly important component of economic growth strategies worldwide, particularly as economies seek to diversify beyond traditional manufacturing and agricultural exports. This paper has highlighted Uzbekistan's significant potential to leverage sectors such as IT, tourism, and financial services to drive economic diversification, increase resilience to global shocks, and sustain growth. These sectors not only generate revenue but also create high-quality employment, foster innovation, and encourage technological advancement.

However, to fully realize the benefits of service exports, Uzbekistan needs targeted policies. Investment in digital infrastructure is crucial to support the growth of IT and other digital services. Policies promoting the development of broadband networks, data centers, and cybersecurity frameworks will enable Uzbekistan to become a competitive player in the global digital economy. Additionally, fostering innovation through incentives for startups and technology companies can catalyze growth in emerging fields like fintech, e-commerce, and digital health.

Building a skilled workforce is another critical factor. Service sectors require specialized skills, and Uzbekistan must focus on aligning educational programs with industry needs. Partnerships with educational institutions, industry stakeholders, and international organizations can help develop a talent pool that meets the demands of the service export market. Continuous upskilling initiatives will also ensure that the workforce can adapt to rapid technological changes.

As global demand for services continues to rise, investing in service sector growth is essential for Uzbekistan's economic stability and development. By implementing policies that promote infrastructure, innovation, and human capital, Uzbekistan can harness the full potential of service exports, positioning itself as a competitive and resilient economy in an increasingly service-oriented global market.

References

1. International Monetary Fund. (2023). The Role of Service Exports in Economic Growth: A Global Perspective. Retrieved from <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/research/Service-Exports>.
2. World Bank. (2022). Global Economic Impacts of Service Sector Growth. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/research/economic-impacts-service-sector>.
3. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD). (2022). Trends in Service Exports and Global Economic Development. Retrieved from <https://unctad.org/publications/trends-service-exports>.
4. Asian Development Bank. (2023). Digital Transformation and Service Exports in Asia. Retrieved from <https://www.adb.org/research/digital-transformation-service-exports-asia>.
5. Francois, J., & Hoekman, B. (2010). "Services Trade and Policy." *Journal of Economic Literature*, 48(3), 642–692.
6. Breinlich, H., & Criscuolo, C. (2011). "International Trade in Services: A Portrait of Importers and Exporters." *Journal of International Economics*, 84(2), 188-206.
7. Park, S. C., & Koo, J. (2020). "The Role of Service Exports and Digitalization in Economic Growth." *Economic Modelling*, 85, 284-297.
8. International Trade Centre (ITC). (2019). SME Competitiveness Outlook 2019: Big Money for Small Business - Financing the Sustainable Development Goals. ITC.
9. World Trade Organization (WTO). (2022). World Trade Report 2022: Trade in Services for Development. WTO.
10. Blanchard, E. J., Bown, C. P., & Johnson, R. C. (2016). "Global Supply Chains and Trade Policy." *American Economic Review*, 106(11), 2925–2956.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokr ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 11

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.